

Design and Implementation of an Embedded System Trainer Module Based on Arduino Microcontroller for Educational and Prototyping Applications

Michael Okon Bassey¹ ✉, Ikechukwu Bismarck Owunna², Aniekan Essienubong Ikpe³

¹ Department of Mechatronics Engineering Technology, Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Ekpene, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria ✉ Email: michael.bassey@akwaibompoly.edu.ng ² Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria

³ Department of Mechanical Engineering Technology, Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Ekpene, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

ARTICLE INFO

©2025 RS Publication

Paper ID: IJASTR-689E15A5CE546

Received: 2025-07-15

Published: 2025-08-19

DOI:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16900558>

Page No: 154-265

ABSTRACT

The Arduino-based embedded system trainer plays a critical role which bridges the gap between theoretical concepts and practical implementation in embedded systems education. The design and implementation of an embedded system trainer module based on Arduino microcontroller for educational and prototyping applications in this research study focuses on the integration of component that is targeting telecommunication applications. The trainer module integrates components such as Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, SIM800L, and Ethernet modules, alongside LEDs, OLED displays, and other peripherals, to facilitate hands-on practical experience in embedded systems. The primary objective is to address the high cost and limited availability of embedded system trainers in educational institutions by providing a low-cost, versatile, and fully functional alternative. The development process involved schematic design using Eagle EDA software, PCB printing, soldering, and rigorous testing. The experiments demonstrated the module's capability to perform tasks like remote LED control, SMS transmission, phone calls, and temperature monitoring, validating its effectiveness for hands-on learning. The results confirm that the trainer meets educational requirements, offering a practical solution to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world applications.

Keywords: Embedded systems, Arduino microcontroller, Telecommunication modules, Low-cost trainer, Hands-on learning

Cite This Paper : Michael Okon Bassey ✉, Ikechukwu Bismarck Owunna and Aniekan Essienubong Ikpe (2025). "Design and Implementation of an Embedded System Trainer Module Based on Arduino Microcontroller for Educational and Prototyping Applications". *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ADVANCED SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL RESEARCH (IJASTR)* ISSN 2249-9954, vol. 15, no. 4, 2025, pp. 254-265. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16900558>

1. Introduction

The foundation of contemporary technical developments and embedded systems are enabled by smart devices in areas such consumer electronics, robotics, automation, and the Internet of Things (Sharma et al., 2023). Today microcontrollers, especially the Arduino platform, have become more popular due to their open-source nature, cost, and user-friendliness, which makes them perfect fit for prototyping and instructional applications (Nayak et al., 2022).

Microcontrollers, like those found in the Arduino platform, are the foundation of embedded system design because of their affordability, usability, and adaptability. Effective training resources are required to close the knowledge gap between theory and practice as the need for qualified embedded system engineers increases (Ifeagwu & Ezema, 2025; Kondaveeti et al., 2021; Akinwolev & Adeoye, 2020). Despite their extensive application, the absence of easily available, adaptable, and reasonably priced training resources frequently makes it difficult for engineering students to move from theoretical concepts to real-world implementation (Sumarah et al., 2024). In engineering education, experiential learning is a critical and essential tool which improves understanding and problem-solving abilities (Chu & Park, 2020). However, the current embedded system trainers are designed with proprietary limits, exorbitant prices, and inadequate coverage of key features like GPIO, ADC, PWM, and communication protocols (UART, I2C, SPI) (Galindo & Rosal, 2019). Additionally, most generic kits might not be flexible enough to be customized for sophisticated applications (Huang et al., 2012). These gaps that is inherent in the current systems necessitate the development of an Arduino-based embedded system trainer module that will balances affordability, functionality, and scalability in engineering education prototyping. The focus of this research study is to develop and deploy an embedded system trainer module based on Arduino platform that goes beyond these restrictions and offer a thorough learning environment with engineering application. This training module will be adaptable to integrate embedded system elements including GPIO, ADC, PWM, and communication interfaces (UART, I2C, SPI). This initiative will promote quick prototyping for practical applications thus making engineering education more accessible by creating an open-source, inexpensive embedded system trainer for mechatronics laboratory.

2. Literature Review

Arduino microcontroller-based embedded system trainers are widely used in both academic and commercial scenario, providing learning environments for embedded systems and Internet of Things principles. Academic trainers prioritize cost-effectiveness and flexibility depending on specific teaching goals, whereas most commercial trainers frequently value solid, ready-to-use systems. In engineering education, embedded system trainers are crucial resources for bridging the gap between theoretical understanding and practical expertise. Academic and commercial systems with differing levels of capability, expense, and complexity have been created (Sharma et al., 2023; Chu & Park, 2023; Yakimov, 2016).

2.1 Academic Trainer Modules

Most custom trainer modules are frequently created by academic institutions in accordance with their curriculum. A typical Arduino-based lab trainer is a concatenation that incorporates sensors, motors, Bluetooth modules, and a display unit (Galindo & Rosal, 2019). According to their research, students' hardware programming and interface abilities were much enhanced by practical experience when the Arduino was incorporated. In a similar vein, Sumarah et al. (2024) addressed the dearth of useful resources in microcontroller courses by creating an Arduino Uno R3 trainer with three inputs and outputs. The module's usability and efficacy in

teaching fundamental microcontroller principles were validated and they can be deployed to various purposes like seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Arduino Shields -a. Ethernet, b. Wireless, and c. Motor Driver

Using an Arduino Uno, Valdy and Abidin (2023) developed a PLC trainer board that shows how effective it is for teaching electrical engineering students in logic gate operations. The trainer demonstrated that inexpensive Arduino solutions might take the place of pricey PLC trainers by integrating optocoupler circuits and relay modules. An analog and digital trainer for microprocessor programming was presented in another study by Sulistiyo et al. (2021). It received an 84.37% validation score and 88.49% positive student comments, demonstrating its applicability for self-directed learning.

2.2 Commercial and Industry-Oriented Trainers

Scalability and professional-grade features are some of the frequently emphasized by commercial trainers who market them. For instance, Sharma et al. (2023) developed an Arduino-based embedded system module which integrates motor drivers, temperature sensors, and gas sensors onto a single PCB. Their design has educational use while aiming for industrial prototype. Prasanna et al. (2021) developed a modular IoT trainer board with several power supply options (5V, 9V, and 12V) that interfaces with Arduino Mega, HC-05 (Bluetooth), and NodeMCU (Wi-Fi). The developed system was one of the simplified methods that remained student-friendly while adapting to sophisticated IoT applications. However, most commercial trainers often suffer from exorbitant costs and proprietary limitations. For instance, the investigation of Khalid et al. (2024) observed that specialized proprietary trainers like their voice-controlled DC motor module with 96% media expert approval are often application-specific, limiting broader educational use. In contrast, most academic designs prioritize modularity with affordability which makes them more adaptable for diverse learning environments.

2.3 Comparison of Microcontroller Platforms

Many microcontroller platforms vary in performance, architecture, and suitability for educational purposes. The most widely used platforms include Arduino, PIC, ARM, and Raspberry Pi.

Arduino: Arduino is the most popular platform that is deployed in embedded system education. This is due to its open-source nature, ease of use, and extensive community support (Nayak et al., 2022). Arduino based on Atmel AVR microcontrollers (e.g., ATmega328) and is ideal for beginners (see Figure 2). One of the key advantages of arduino is the simplified Programming operability. Arduino IDE uses a simplified version of C++, making it accessible to beginners (Nayak et al., 2022). Arduino has a rich Peripheral Support with built-in libraries for GPIO, PWM, UART, I2C, and SPI which reduces coding complexity (Galindo & Rosal, 2019)

Figure 2: Arduino uno

PIC Microcontrollers: PIC microcontrollers, such as the PIC16F877 and PIC18F452, are frequently utilized in industrial settings because of their dependability and low power consumption (Rankovska & Goranov, 2020). PIC Microcontroller as seen in Figure 3, provide effective Hardware Control that is utilized in most software tools. For real-time control systems, PICs are recommended for engineering application prototyping (Rankovska & Goranov, 2020). PIC microcontroller is economical for large-scale manufacturing because it is less expensive in term of unit cost when compared to Arduino (Rankovska & Goranov, 2020). However, due to their limited support for high-level languages (HLL) and intricate assembly programming, PICs have a steeper learning curve (Aslam et al., 2019).

Figure 3: PIC microcontroller

ARM-Based Microcontrollers: ARM-Based microcontrollers (see Figure 4) are set of central processing unit system that has reduced instruction architecture (RISC). ARM Cortex-M series (e.g., STM32) dominate high-performance embedded systems market that has robust features ranging from high processing power which is suitable for RTOS, DSP, and IoT applications (Chu & Park, 2020).

Figure 4: ARM-Based microcontrollers

They are incorporated with high energy efficiency which is suitable for battery-operated devices. Despite their advantages, ARM-based microcontroller platforms require advanced programming skills like embedded C and RTOS thus making them less suitable for beginners (Chu & Park, 2020).

Raspberry Pi: Pi is a single-board computer (SBC) rather than a microcontroller, offering which offers full OS Support that runs on Linux which offers an enabling environment for Python, Java, and web-based applications (Chu & Park, 2020). It offers a High Computational Power that is used for AI, computer vision, and network applications. However, Raspberry Pi is overkill for simple embedded tasks, consumes more power, and lacks real-time performance (Chu & Park, 2020). The summary of the Raspberry Pi and other platform can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1: Platform comparison summary

Platform	Pros	Cons	Best For
Arduino	Easy to use, low cost, open-source	Limited processing power	Beginners, basic embedded systems
PIC	Low power, reliable, cost-effective	Complex programming	Industrial control systems
ARM	High performance, energy-efficient	Steep learning curve	Advanced IoT, RTOS applications
Raspberry Pi	Full OS support, high compute power	High cost, power consumption	AI, networking, multimedia

3. Methodology

The methodology for developing the Arduino-based embedded system trainer follows a structured approach to ensure functionality, scalability, and educational effectiveness. For requirement analysis, key functionalities (GPIO, ADC, PWM, UART, I2C, SPI) were identified.

3.1 System Development Model

In the Modular Design Approach, the trainer was designed as a stackable, expandable system with interchangeable modules. The Core of modules include: Input/Output (I/O) Module (buttons, switches, LEDs), Sensors & Actuators Module (temperature, motion, motors). While the Communication Module involved UART, I2C, SPI, and Bluetooth. The process was

involved which range from Prototyping & Validation, Breadboard testing for initial circuit verification and PCB design for final hardware integration. Table 2 is the illustration of the material component that was in the research study.

Table 2: Material component

Material	Quantity
4*4 Keypad Module	1
LEDs	5
Buzzer	1
4 Digit 7 Segment Display	1
OLED Graphics Display	1
Bluetooth Module	1
Wi-Fi Module	1
Ethernet Module	1
GSM Module	1
Resistors	5
Arduino NANO	1
Digital Multimeter	1
Soldering Iron	1
Soldering Lead	1
Hand Drill	1
Prototyping Board	1
Breadboard	1
Jumper Wires	20

Telecommunication Board Segment: This contains the SIM800L, Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, Ethernet modules, OLED display, 4-digit 7-segment display, LEDs and resistors (see illustration in Figure 5 and 6).

Figure 5: Schematic diagram of the telecommunication board segment

Figure 6: Complete diagram of the telecommunication board segment

4. Results and Discussion

Performance evaluation of the trainer module.

The experiments conducted from the research study demonstrates the successful design and development of an embedded system trainer module that is based on the Arduino microcontroller system. The trainer module was integrated with various communication and display components, including Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, SIM800L, Ethernet modules, and OLED displays, to facilitate hands-on practical experience in embedded systems. The results of the experiments clearly validate the module's functionality, reliability, and educational value.

Experiment 1: Interfacing the HC-05 Bluetooth Module with Arduino and LED

The focus of the experiment was to use the HC-05 Bluetooth module to remotely operate an LED. The outcomes verified that an Android application with Bluetooth capability could be used to switch the LED on and off. The successful deployment demonstrates the module's capacity to support wireless communication, which is essential for contemporary embedded systems. Additionally, the experiment showed how simple it is to integrate Bluetooth modules with Arduino, which makes it appropriate for Internet of Things applications like remote device control and home automation. The system's ability to react quickly to orders from the mobile app highlights how useful Bluetooth-based control systems are in everyday situations. Circuit diagram of the Hc-05 Bluetooth module interfaced with the LED is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Circuit Diagram of the Hc-05 bluetooth module interfaced with the LED

Experiment 2: Interfacing the TM1637 (4-Digit 7-Segment Display) with Arduino

The goal was to use the 4-digit, 7-segment display to create a simple clock. The experiment demonstrated the module's capacity to handle digital output devices by successfully displaying real-time clock functionality. The accuracy of the display and the simplicity of configuring the Arduino to control the TM1637 module suggest that this configuration may be expanded to include digital readouts, timers, and counters. The experiment also showed how well the trainer can reduce intricate interface chores, which makes it a useful teaching tool for microcontroller programming and digital electronics. The circuit diagram of the 4-Digit & Segment display interfaced with the Arduino is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Circuit diagram of the 4-digit & segment display interfaced with the arduino

Experiment 3: Interfacing the SIM800L with Arduino to Send an SMS

The GSM module's text message sending capabilities were examined in this experiment. The SIM800L's connection with the Arduino microcontroller was validated when it successfully sent SMS messages to a pre-specified phone number. The outcomes demonstrate the module's potential for use in remote notification applications including industrial monitoring systems and security warnings. Because the SIM800L needed steady power and resistor networks to function reliably, the experiment also highlighted the significance of appropriate voltage control and signal conditioning. For students studying real-world restrictions in embedded system design, this discovery is essential. Figure 9 shows the circuit diagram of the SIM800L interfaced with the Arduino to send an SMS.

Figure 9: Circuit diagram of the SIM800L interfaced with the Arduino to send an SMS

Experiment 4: Interfacing the SIM800L with Arduino to Read an SMS

The functionality of the module to receive and display incoming SMS messages was demonstrated in the experiment. The outcomes demonstrated that user involvement was made possible by the system's ability to analyse and transmit messages to the serial monitor. Applications such as remote data logging and automatic response systems require this feature. The experiment also demonstrated how crucial error management is in communication protocols because even small processing lags may have an impact on performance. Students researching real-time embedded systems will find these ideas useful. The build circuit diagram of the SIM800L interfaced with the Arduino to read an SMS is illustrated in Figure 10.

Figure 10: the build circuit diagram of the SIM800L interfaced with the Arduino to read an SMS

Experiment 5: Interfacing the SIM800L with Arduino to Make a Phone Call

The GSM module successfully dialled a pre-programmed number to start voice calls. The module's communications capabilities, which may be used in automated calling services and emergency alert systems, were confirmed by this experiment. The findings also made clear how important it is for voice-based apps to have appropriate audio interface and noise reduction. The experiment connects theoretical understanding with practical application, providing a useful introduction to embedded communications systems. The circuit diagram of the SIM800L interfaced with the Arduino to make a phone call presented in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Circuit diagram of the SIM800L interfaced with the Arduino to make a phone call.

Experiment 6: Interfacing the SIM800L with Arduino to Receive a Phone Call

From this experiment, after successfully identifying incoming calls, the system sent call information to the serial monitor. The SIM800L module's ability to communicate in both directions was demonstrated in this experiment, which is crucial for interactive applications such as call-based control systems. The findings also highlighted the significance of interrupt management in real-time communication, which is a fundamental idea in the teaching of embedded systems. The circuit diagram of the SIM800L interfaced with the Arduino to receive a phone call is presented in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Circuit diagram of the SIM800L interfaced with the Arduino to receive a phone call.

Experiment 7: Interfacing the HC-05 Bluetooth Module with Arduino, LED, and DC Motor and Creating a Thermometer Using the TM1637, DHT11, and Arduino

An LED and a DC motor were both controlled over Bluetooth in this lengthy experiment. The outcomes demonstrated that the system could use wireless instructions to independently operate a number of devices. For robotics and automation applications, where remote actuator control is crucial, this experiment is especially pertinent. The trainer's adaptability in teaching intricate embedded system interactions is demonstrated by the effective integration of several components. Additionally, Real-time temperature data were successfully shown on the seven-segment display during the experiment. The outcomes confirmed a basic idea in embedded systems: The integration of sensor data with output devices. Additionally, the experiment

showed that the trainer could teach real-time feedback systems, data processing, and sensor interface. Applications for environmental monitoring can benefit from the system's precision and reactivity.

5. Conclusion and Future Work

This study successfully designed and implemented an embedded system trainer module based on the Arduino Nano microcontroller, specifically targeting telecommunication applications with Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, SIM800L, and Ethernet modules. The trainer was developed to address the high cost and limited availability of practical learning tools in academic institutions. Through systematic hardware integration and software programming, the module demonstrated its capability to perform various embedded system experiments, including wireless communication, SMS transmission, phone call handling, and sensor interfacing. Testing confirmed that the trainer meets the functional requirements for hands-on education, providing students with a cost-effective platform to bridge theoretical knowledge and real-world applications.

To further improve the trainer's functionality and educational value, future work should focus on IoT Integration. Incorporating additional IoT sensors (e.g., environmental, motion, and biometric sensors) can help expand hands-on applications in smart systems. Another improvement on the existing work should be on the areas of advanced wireless modules which can be upgraded to LoRa, Zigbee, or NB-IoT for broader wireless communication experiments. Additionally, introduction of enhanced debugging features to module trainer can serve as platform that can integrate onboard debugging tools (e.g., logic analyzers or serial monitors) which can assist mechatronics students in troubleshooting.

References

- Akinwale, O., & Adeoye, O. S. (2020). Designing Embedded Systems with Arduino Microcontrollers: A Way Forward for Technological Advancement in Nigeria. *International Journal of Electrical and Electronics Engineering*, 7, 1-5.
- Aslam, S., Ahsan, M., Hannan, S., Hamza, M., & Jaffery, M. (2019, February). Development of a software based PIC24F series microcontroller educational trainer. In 2019 International Conference on Engineering and Emerging Technologies (ICEET) (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- Chu, Y., & Park, J. H. (2023). Efficient learning modules for embedded system. *International Journal of Electrical Engineering & Education*, 60(2_suppl), 110-119.
- Chu, Y., & Park, J. H. (2023). Efficient learning modules for embedded system. *International Journal of Electrical Engineering & Education*, 60(2_suppl), 110-119.
- Galindo, J. A., & Rosal, J. E. (2019). Development Of a Microcontroller Laboratory Trainer Module for Engineering Students. *Slongan*, 4(1), 8-8.
- Huang, H. H., Liu, C. Y., Huang, M. C., Ko, I. C., & Lee, J. M. (2012). Digital I/O Training Kit Development for Arduino Platforms. *Applied Mechanics and Materials*, 214, 649-653.
- Ifeagwu, E. N., & Ezema, D. C. (2025). Affordable Micro-Controller Arduino-Based Board

Experimental Training Kit Implementation in Nigerian Universities. *Caritas Journal of Engineering Technology*, 4(1).

Khalid, M., Fathiah, F., & Gufran, G. I. Y. (2024). Trainer Kit Module for DC Motor Speed Control Using Voice Commands Based on Arduino. *JURNAL EDUNITRO Jurnal Pendidikan Teknik Elektro*, 4(2), 85-94.

Kondaveeti, H. K., Kumaravelu, N. K., Vanambathina, S. D., Mathe, S. E., & Vappangi, S. (2021). A systematic literature review on prototyping with Arduino: Applications, challenges, advantages, and limitations. *Computer Science Review*, 40, 100364.

Nayak, A., Hiremath, N., Garagad, V., & Chickerur, S. (2022, March). Teaching microcontrollers-using Arduino as a platform. In 2022 IEEE global engineering education conference (EDUCON) (pp. 941-945). IEEE.

Prasanna, K. R., Seetharaman, R., Lakshmanan, H. M., Karthik, G., & Anandan, K. (2021, May). Design and fabrication of printed circuit board for IoT applications. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1916, No. 1, p. 012234). IOP Publishing.

Rankovska, V. V., & Goranov, G. D. (2020). PIC microcontroller module in a flexible microprocessor development system. In 2020 55th International Scientific Conference on Information, Communication and Energy Systems and Technologies (ICEST) (pp. 3-6). IEEE.

Sharma, H., Prajapat, H., Yadav, J., Bhatra, L., & Deo, A. (2023). Arduino-Based Embedded System Module. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology (IJRASET)*.

Sharma, H., Prajapat, H., Yadav, J., Bhatra, L., & Deo, A. (2023). Arduino-Based Embedded System Module. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology (IJRASET)*. 11(4). 3403- 3408

Sulistiyo, E., Meduri, N. R. H., Achmad, F., Wibawa, S. C., & Spoettli, G. (2021, May). The Development of Analog and Digital Trainer Base on Arduino Uno in Microprocessor Programming Subjects. In *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* (Vol. 1125, No. 1, p. 012077). IOP Publishing.

Sumarah, J., Wulandari, A. T., Tafrikhatin, A., Benedi, J., & Pambudi, A. R. (2024). Making an Arduino Uno R3 Trainer as A Learning Support Tool in The Electronics Study Program. *Jurnal E-Komtek (Elektro-Komputer-Teknik)*, 8(1), 40-45.

Valdy, R. C. A., & Abidin, Z. (2023). Prototipe Papan Trainer PLC Sederhana Berbasis Arduino Uno Dengan Menggunakan Software Outsel Studio. *Jurnal JEETech*, 4(2), 127-138.

Yakimov, P. I. (2016). Open-source platforms application in introductory embedded systems teaching. In 2016 XXV International Scientific Conference Electronics (ET) (pp. 1-4). IEEE.